

Determining the Clinico-Etiologic Characteristics of Infants Presenting With Jaundice: A Retrospective Study

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Received: 12-02-2024 / Revised: 15-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: To determine the clinical and etiological characteristics of infants presenting with jaundice at a tertiary care hospital.

Material and Methods: This retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics, MGM Medical College, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India for one year. A total of 400 cases were enrolled for the study. Neonates with jaundice admitted in NICU or neonatology ward during study period, with serum bilirubin more than 10 mg/dL were included. Neonates with jaundice not admitted in NICU, attending outpatient department only, neonates with jaundice opted discharge against medical advice and parents not willing to participate in this study were excluded.

Results: During study period, 400 newborns were considered for present study, as they were satisfying inclusion and exclusion criteria. Out of 400 jaundiced neonates, 236 (59%) were males and 164 (41%) were females. Among 400 newborns studied, 342 (85.5%) were born at term gestation and the remaining 58 (14.5%) were preterm babies as shown in Table 1. Table 2 shows that out of 400 newborns included in this study, majority of the babies had birth weight ≥ 2500 gm (80%). Only 40 babies had birth weight < 2500 gm (20%). Table 3 shows that physiological jaundice constituted the major (40.5%) etiological factor in neonatal jaundice. This was followed by ABO incompatibility which constituted 20%. of these 50% were due to OA incompatibility and 50% were due to OB incompatibility. Other common causes were Rh incompatibility (16.5%), sepsis (8%), idiopathic (5%) and prematurity (4%). Neonatal jaundice was attributed to cephalhematoma in 16 (4%) cases. Breastfeeding jaundice was found in 8 (2%) cases.

Conclusion: We concluded that the less common causes are cephalhematoma, breast feeding jaundice and hemolytic anemia. Understanding the etiological and risk factors for neonatal jaundice in our setting helps in prioritizing the group of neonates who require more intensive monitoring for early identification and timely management of this condition.

Keywords: Infants Jaundice.

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Introduction

Neonatal jaundice, characterized by the yellow discoloration of the skin and sclerae, is a common condition affecting a significant proportion of newborns worldwide. This condition results from the accumulation of bilirubin, a byproduct of red blood cell breakdown, in the blood. While jaundice is often benign and self-limiting, it can sometimes indicate underlying pathological conditions and, if left untreated, can lead to severe complications such as acute bilirubin encephalopathy and kernicterus. [1-4] The aetiology of neonatal jaundice is multifactorial and varies based on geographical, genetic, and socioeconomic factors. Common causes include physiological jaundice, which is a normal transitional phenomenon occurring in most newborns, and pathological jaundice, which may be due to haemolytic diseases, infections, metabolic

disorders, and congenital anomalies. The distinction between physiological and pathological jaundice is critical for timely and appropriate management. Physiological jaundice typically manifests within the first week of life and is characterized by a gradual increase in bilirubin levels, peaking around the third to fifth day in term infants, and slightly later in preterm infants. [5-9] This form of jaundice resolves spontaneously as the newborn's liver matures and improves its ability to conjugate and excrete bilirubin. In contrast, pathological jaundice often appears within the first 24 hours after birth or persists beyond the first week. Common pathological causes include ABO or Rh incompatibility, leading to hemolytic disease of the newborn, which can result in significant hyperbilirubinemia. Other etiological factors

include G6PD deficiency, a genetic disorder that predisposes neonates to hemolysis, and sepsis, which can interfere with bilirubin metabolism and excretion. [10-12] The management of neonatal jaundice involves a combination of clinical assessment and laboratory investigations to determine the underlying cause and severity of hyperbilirubinemia. Phototherapy remains the mainstay of treatment for significant hyperbilirubinemia, while exchange transfusion is reserved for severe cases where there is a risk of bilirubin-induced neurological damage. Recent advances in the understanding of neonatal jaundice have led to the development of more accurate diagnostic tools and treatment protocols aimed at reducing the incidence of severe hyperbilirubinemia and its complications. For instance, transcutaneous bilirubinometry has become a widely used, non-invasive method for estimating bilirubin levels, allowing for more frequent monitoring and early intervention. This study aims to elucidate the clinico-etiological profile of neonates presenting with jaundice in a tertiary care center. By identifying the common causes and risk factors associated with neonatal jaundice, we hope to contribute to the development of targeted strategies for its prevention and management, ultimately improving neonatal outcomes. [13,14]

Material and Methods

This retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics, MGM Medical College, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India for one year. A total of 400 cases were enrolled for the study. Proper approval was taken from institutional ethical committee. Neonates with jaundice admitted in NICU or neonatology ward during study period, with serum bilirubin more than 10 mg/dL were included. Neonates with jaundice not admitted in NICU, attending outpatient department only, neonates with jaundice opted discharge against medical advice and parents not willing to participate in this study were excluded.

Methodology

The purpose of the present study was explained to parents and a written consent was taken for participation. Detailed history was taken for all babies along with maternal, antenatal and delivery details. Thorough physical examination was done

and the relevant investigations were carried out. General data including age, birth weight, age at detection of jaundice, breast feeding status, family history of jaundice was noted. Jaundice was ascertained by clinical methods. This was confirmed with the help of biochemical tests. Serum bilirubin was estimated by Van den Bergh method. Further investigations were not carried out on those babies who were having physiological jaundice. Blood grouping and Rh typing of baby and mother were done. Cord blood bilirubin and hemoglobin, direct Coomb's test (DCT) and bilirubin monitoring were done whenever there was a setting for Rh incompatibility. In case of ABO incompatibility, DCT was done and bilirubin monitored. Other investigations like hemoglobin level, peripheral smear and reticulocyte count were done when indicated. If these tests showed features of hemolysis and there was no blood group incompatibility, G6PD assay, sickling test, hemoglobin electrophoresis and osmotic fragility test were done wherever appropriate. G6PD was done by fluorescent technique, 2% sodium metabisulphite was used for sickling test. Osmotic fragility test using serial dilutions of sodium chloride was done. Neonates who were suspected to have sepsis were investigated by complete blood count, septic screen and blood and urine cultures.

Results

During study period, 400 newborns were considered for present study, as they were satisfying inclusion and exclusion criteria. Out of 400 jaundiced neonates, 236 (59%) were males and 164 (41%) were females. Among 400 newborns studied, 342 (85.5%) were born at term gestation and the remaining 58 (14.5%) were preterm babies as shown in Table 1. Table 2 shows that out of 400 newborns included in this study, majority of the babies had birth weight ≥ 2500 gm (80%). Only 40 babies had birth weight < 2500 gm (20%). Table 3 shows that physiological jaundice constituted the major (40.5%) etiological factor in neonatal jaundice. This was followed by ABO incompatibility which constituted 20%. of these 50% were due to OA incompatibility and 50% were due to OB incompatibility. Other common causes were Rh incompatibility (16.5%), sepsis (8%), idiopathic (5%) and prematurity (4%). Neonatal jaundice was attributed to cephalhematoma in 16 (4%) cases. Breastfeeding jaundice was found in 8 (2%) cases.

Table 1: Distribution of Jaundiced neonates according to gestational age, (n=400).

Gestational age (weeks)	N	Percentage (%)
>37	342	85.5
34-36	38	9.5
30-34	20	5
Total	400	100

Table 2: Distribution of jaundiced neonates according to birth weight, (n=400).

Birth weight (gm)	N	Percentage (%)
1000-1499	20	5
1500-2499	60	15
≥2500	320	80
Total	400	100

Table 3: Etiology of neonatal jaundice.

Etiology	N	Percentage (%)
Physiological jaundice	162	40.5
ABO incompatibility	80	20
Rh incompatibility	66	16.5
Sepsis	32	8
Idiopathic	20	5
Prematurity	16	4
Cephalhematoma	16	4
Breastfeeding jaundice	8	2
Total	400	100

Discussion

Neonatal jaundice is one of the most common causes of hospitalization of neonates in the first month after birth. In most cases, neonatal jaundice is transient and usually resolving at the end of the first week after birth. But when severe hyperbilirubinemia is present, there is a potential risk for acute bilirubin encephalopathy and kernicterus. This can lead to death in the first months, and infants who are still alive often suffer from mental retardation, movement and balance disorders, seizures, hearing loss at high frequencies, and speech impairment. So, timely diagnosis and treatment of neonatal jaundice are very important to prevent further complications. In this study, out of the total 400 neonates with jaundice, 59% were males and only 41% were females. The results match the earlier studies done by Effiong et al, Narang et al and Korejo et al where majority of the babies were males. [13-15] Majority of the babies studied were of term gestation. Only 14.5% were born preterm. A higher percentage of premature babies was found in studies done by Bhutani et al and Singhal et al. [16,17] In the present study, majority of the babies had birth weight ≥ 2500 gm. Only 20% of the babies had birth weight less than 2500 gm. As our study had 85.5% term babies, majority (80%) had normal birth weight. In this study, physiological jaundice was found to be the major etiological factor i.e., 162 out of the total 400 babies (40.5%). This is in concordance to the study done by Bahl et al, wherein the physiological jaundice was observed in majority of the patients (63.8%). [18] Studies done by Singhal et al and Merchant et al observed physiological jaundice in 16.7% and 25.3% of the total cases respectively. [17,19] This was followed by ABO incompatibility as the second leading cause of neonatal jaundice in our study (20%). This is in concordance to the studies done by Verma et al and Merchant et al,

wherein ABO incompatibility contributed to 22.6% of the cases. [19,20] The number of OA and OB incompatibility cases was equal in this study. Bahl et al had reported a higher incidence of OA incompatibility (60%) whereas Bajpai PC et al had observed higher percentage of OB incompatibility. [18,21] After ABO incompatibility, Rh incompatibility was found to be responsible for 16.5% of the total cases. Bajpai PC et al reported an incidence of 1.6% for Rh incompatibility while Verma et al observed Rh incompatibility in 9.8% of the total cases. Thus, ABO incompatibility was more prevalent than Rh incompatibility. This is in concordance with older studies done abroad. [22,23] Similar findings were reported from India too. [17,19,20]

In this study, sepsis constituted 8% of the total cases studied. This is in concordance to earlier studies which showed a similar trend. Sepsis was found to be the cause of neonatal jaundice in 8% of neonates by Merchant et al, [11]. 6% by Verma et al and in 9.6% of neonates by Narang et al. [19,20,14] No known cause could be established in 5% of the total cases. Studies done by Singal et al and Bahl et al observed that idiopathic jaundice was present in 8.8% to 57% of the total cases. [17,18] Prematurity as a cause of neonatal jaundice was found in 4% of the total cases. Cephalhematoma was 4% of the cases with neonatal jaundice. This is comparable to the study done by Narang et al which found that cephalhematoma was responsible for 6.3% of the total cases with neonatal jaundice. [14] There were 8 (2%) cases of breastfeeding jaundice which regressed after improving the frequency of breastfeeding.

Conclusion

This study concludes that physiological jaundice is the most common cause of neonatal jaundice in our

hospital. This is followed by ABO incompatibility, sepsis, Rh incompatibility and idiopathic cases. Less common causes are cephalhematoma, breast feeding jaundice and hemolytic anemia. Understanding the etiological and risk factors for neonatal jaundice in our setting helps in prioritizing the group of neonates who require more intensive monitoring for early identification and timely management of this condition.

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